

Mapping language economy strategies in Spanish political discourse on X

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates language economy strategies in Spanish political discourse on X, analysing how users optimize communication. Through analysis of posts, we identify patterns of linguistic adaptation across syntactic and morphological dimensions. The research combines computational linguistics with traditional discourse analysis to examine strategy distribution, comprehensibility, and effectiveness. Results reveal a preference for syntactic strategies over morphological modifications. Message comprehensibility remains high despite substantial compression, challenging assumptions about the economy-clarity trade-off. Thread depth analysis shows peak strategy diversity at moderate depths, suggesting an optimal complexity point in digital political discourse. The study extends platform vernacular theory by demonstrating how political actors adapt linguistic strategies while maintaining effectiveness. These findings contribute to understanding how languages adapt to digital environments and have implications for political communication strategies, platform design, and digital literacy education.

1. Introduction

Language economy refers to the creative and efficient use of communication strategies that balance brevity, clarity, and adaptability. Language economy in the context of digital platforms is reflected in the user's ability to convey meaning with minimal effort while leveraging available tools, technologies, and social norms to enhance expression. In digital platforms, it goes beyond concise wording to include multimodal tools (like emojis, GIFs, and visuals), real-time conversational mimicry, and creative workarounds for imposed limitations such as community rules or cultural expectations. The dynamic process fosters both innovation and ambiguity, making language more flexible, expressive, and context-dependent in modern communication. Scholars have already discussed this phenomenon in English, Russian, and German online discourse (P. von, 2000; Steinhauer, 2000; Valgina, 2003). However, the unique features of Spanish political communication remain underexplored, particularly in social media contexts.

Recent theoretical developments in digital communication have emphasized how platform-specific affordances shape linguistic adaptation. Nagy and Neff's (2015) concept of imagined affordances illuminates how users perceive and utilize X's constraints for political communication. This theoretical framework helps explain the systematic adaptation of language economy strategies observed in political discourse. Furthermore, Varis and Blommaert's (2015) work on digital sociolinguistics demonstrates how platform constraints interact with social and political factors to create unique patterns of linguistic innovation.

The study of language economy in Spanish political discourse pays special attention due to Spanish's rich morphological and

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syntactic features, which offer distinctive possibilities for linguistic adaptation in digital environments. Being one of the world's most widely spoken languages, Spanish political discourse exerts substantial influence both regionally and internationally. Understanding how Spanish speakers employ language economy strategies in digital political communication can reveal patterns that differ significantly from those observed in other languages. The present study addresses this research gap by examining two key questions:

- How are the syntactic and morphological strategies of linguistic economy used in Spanish political discourse on X, and what patterns emerge in their combination?
- What is the relationship between thread depth, strategy diversity, and message comprehensibility in Spanish political discourse on X?

2. Language economy and digital discourse

2.1. Political communication and X

Digital discourse comprises various forms of communication that occur in digital environments through digital technologies (Thurlow & Mroczek, 2011). It is marked by a blend of oral and written elements, the presence of discourse markers (Yefanov & Osokin, 2022; Zhang & Li, 2017) and the emergence of new, digitally mediated practices (Rusko, 2013). The hybridity of the digital discourse on X allows for a rich and nuanced mode of communication that goes outside the traditional characteristics of spoken and written language. This is evident in the use of acronyms, emoticons, and other nonverbal cues that mimic face-to-face interaction within the digital realm (Petroni, 2009).

Platform vernacular theory (Gibbs et al., 2015) suggests that each social media platform develops distinct communicative norms and practices. In political discourse, these platform-specific patterns interact with broader political communication strategies, creating unique hybrid forms of expression (KhosraviNik, 2017) and becoming the new digitally mediated paradigm of communication (KhosraviNik, 2022). Interestingly, studies have found that individual users, rather than platforms or user groups, primarily drive variation in social media discourse (Sardinha, 2022). This suggests that political messaging strategies must account for the diverse ways individuals engage with and interpret content across different platforms.

When it comes to political discourse on X, it shares many characteristics of the language typical of computer-mediated communication, such as abbreviations, omission of vowels, use of emoticons and special symbols (Escandell Vidal, 2023; Moraldo, 2012; Siever, 2006). These features fall into the classification proposed by Herring (2012), which includes typography, orthography, morphology, and syntax. These linguistic features contribute to the distinct style of political discourse on X, where brevity and immediacy are valued, and users often employ creative strategies to convey complex ideas within the limitations of the platform and the nature of natural communication.

2.2. Language economy and X

Language economy is another key aspect of digital discourse on X. The principle of least effort is one of the linguistic laws, also known as the law of linguistic economy. It has been a topic of interest in linguistics for many years. In studying it, researchers have approached this phenomenon from various perspectives, including ease of articulation (Passy, 1891), the principle of least effort (Zipf, 2012), the law of least effort (Martinet, 2005), the economy of linguistic resources (Jespersen, 2007). Sweet (2014), like Passy, investigated the tendency of linguistic economy in the phonetics of different languages, concluding that omission of final consonants in some languages does not affect the receiver's comprehension of an utterance.

Jespersen (2007), highlighting specific cases of economy of speech, maintains that economic languages can achieve greater expressiveness with less effort. Moreno Cabrera (2002) stated that linguistic economy is a principle whereby the speaker tends to preserve their effort when communicating. Thus, when choosing between several options to express the same idea, the speaker will choose the one that requires the least energy. It should be noted that the economy of language means not only a saving of effort on the part of the speaker but also a tendency towards a rapid and unambiguous understanding of the information by the listener.

The concept of language economy has also been subject to substantial critique. Many linguists argue that the economy is just one of many competing forces shaping language, and it is often constrained or overridden by other factors such as redundancy, expressiveness, and social norms. One major challenge to the principle of economy is the inherent redundancy in language. Redundancy ensures clarity and comprehension, particularly in contexts where ambiguity or noise could disrupt communication. Linguistic systems often encode redundant information at multiple levels, such as agreement in gender, number, or tense (Gibson et al., 2019). Redundancy may seem inefficient; nevertheless, it aids in error recovery and comprehension, especially in spoken communication where contextual cues may be unclear. This functional role of redundancy suggests that efficiency must often be balanced with reliability in communication. Another key criticism is that language frequently prioritizes expressiveness over brevity. In many contexts, speakers and writers use elaboration, repetition and figurative language to convey emotional depth, tone, or aesthetic value. Horn (2014) highlights that such pragmatic concerns as politeness, emphasis, or persuasion often drive such lexical choices.

Digital communication offers a modern context where language economy and expressiveness coexist. Social media platforms like X encourage brevity, rapid communication and informal expression, providing a space for users to experiment with language (Borisova, 2020). Users often prioritize creativity and emotional expressiveness over strict economy. Emojis, elongated spellings, and playful misspellings convey tone and personality, adding layers of complexity rather than reducing effort.

Several scholars have proposed classifications of linguistic economic strategies. For example, P. von (1988) identifies forms of

language economy, such as elliptical (omitting elements), compressed (reducing language to essentials), and implicit (conveying meaning through implication). Also, Glukhova (1984) views linguistic economy as a transformation of morphological and syntactic structures, including compound nouns and infinitive clauses, while Anis (2007), in studying French digital discourse, identifies features like omission of accents, substitution of letters, phonetic spelling, truncations, suppression of vowels, syllabograms (rebus writing), and numerals substituting for syllables. Paredes (2007) states that there are different types of linguistic economy, that is, phonological, morphological, lexical, semantic and syntactic. Furthermore, Thurlow and Mroczek (2012) list mechanisms in digital discourse like shortenings, contractions, clippings, acronyms, letter/number homophones, non-conventional spelling, accent stylization, non-alphabetic symbols, and emoticons. Additionally, Moraldo (2012) notes economic writing patterns and posts, including letter and punctuation, repetition for emphasis, emoticons, abbreviations, morphologically reduced word forms, and the use of special characters, and Crystal (2011) identifies features such as fusions, special symbols, abbreviations, ellipsis, omission of punctuation, and emoticons, contributing to an informal communication tone. Moraldo's (2012) and Anis's (2007) studies, for instance, concentrate on French and Italian, highlighting a gap in research on Spanish language economy.

Thus, the existing classifications may not adequately address the critical perspectives concerning the potential negative impacts of language economy on comprehension and language standards. There is a need for a more nuanced understanding that incorporates both the functional benefits and the potential drawbacks of language economic strategies.

3. Corpus and methods

3.1. Corpus

In this study, within a period from March 24 to March 27, 2022, we gathered a corpus of X's posts and comments, focusing on Spanish political discourse. The corpus consists of 1208 posts and comments, with an average of 21.53 words per post or comment, a maximum of 60 words, and a minimum of 1. We selected posts and comments surrounding a significant geopolitical event—the military assault in Ukraine—due to its substantial global impact and the high engagement it generated among Spanish social media users. This event provided a particularly representative moment in political discourse, capturing diverse political opinions and communication strategies characteristic of Spanish political dialogue on social media. The selection of this specific time period was strategic, as it coincided with intense international diplomatic activity and significant Spanish political engagement with the conflict, generating substantial discourse across the political spectrum. This period saw a heightened political discussion that required users to communicate complex diplomatic, military, and humanitarian concepts within platform constraints, making it ideal for studying language economy strategies in political discourse.

To ensure corpus relevance, we implemented a multilayered filtering system incorporating carefully curated keywords and hashtags. The dataset includes both original posts and comments to politicians' statements regarding the selected event, providing a comprehensive view of political discourse dynamics during this critical period. Corpus construction relied on a multilayered filtering procedure based on event-related keywords, references to political actors and institutions, and recurrent hashtags associated with the selected political context. The filtering criteria were designed to capture discourse related to the military assault in Ukraine while avoiding over-restriction that could exclude politically relevant commentary expressed through indirect reference or evaluative framing. Table 1 provides illustrative examples of the lexical items used at each filtering layer. These examples are representative rather than exhaustive and are intended to document the logic of corpus selection rather than to define a closed vocabulary. The inclusion of multiple filtering layers allowed the dataset to capture both explicitly event-focused posts and politically evaluative discourse relying on shared contextual knowledge. This approach ensured thematic coherence while preserving variability in linguistic economy strategies.

The data collection process required Academic API v2 access to X's historical data, as the analysed posts fell outside the standard seven-day access window. We utilized Twarc2, a Python library designed for archiving X data, to extract conversation threads containing political discourse about the selected event. The extraction command gathered complete conversation threads and stored them in JSON format for processing. Our data refinement focused specifically on Spanish language content, using X's language identification parameters to isolate relevant posts. We excluded posts containing URLs or lacking textual content to maintain focus on linguistic patterns rather than multimodal communication. This approach yielded our final corpus of 1208 posts, with comprehensive metadata including timestamps and conversation threading information preserved for analysis.

3.2. Method

Our analysis framework combined computational linguistics with manual verification through a systematic, multi-layered approach. The implementation was carried out using Python 3.8+ with specialized natural language processing tools, primarily

Table 1
Illustrative examples of keywords and hashtags used for corpus filtering.

Category	Examples
Event-related keywords	<i>Ucrania, guerra, invasión, Kiev</i>
Political actors and institutions	<i>Putin, OTAN, UE, gobierno</i>
Hashtags	<i>#NoALaGuerra, #Ucrania, #Rusia</i>

employing spaCy (Honnibal et al., 2020) with its Spanish language model (es_core_news_lg) for linguistic analysis. The data processing pipeline consisted of three main phases: preprocessing, analysis, and validation. During the preprocessing, we cleaned the corpus by removing extraneous elements (URLs, mentions) while preserving linguistic features essential for language economy analysis. Language verification employed a two-step process combining automated detection with manual verification to ensure corpus integrity. While prior research suggests that individual users are primary drivers of variation in social media discourse (Sardinha, 2022), the present study adopts a corpus-level perspective in order to identify emergent regularities arising from aggregated individual linguistic choices rather than modelling user-specific behaviour.

The core analytical framework was implemented through a custom-developed SyntacticEconomyAnalyzer class, which operated across three levels of pattern detection: syntactic, morphological, and contextual. Syntactic analysis included pro-drop detection through morphological inspection of verb forms, identification of parataxis using regular expression patterns, structural compression analysis of multi-clause constructions, dependency parsing for syntactic relationship analysis, and clause boundary detection. Morphological pattern detection targeted clipping (e.g. *profe*, *cole*), extraction of morphological features (person, number, tense), clitic and affix detection, suffix pattern analysis (including diminutives and augmentatives), and identification of initialisms and acronyms using context-aware validation procedures. Contextual analysis focused on thread structure examination, discourse marker validation, and cross-message reference tracking, enabling the modelling of linguistic economy strategies within interactional settings.

In addition to structural and morphological features, the analysis incorporates contextual factors as a core analytical dimension. Context was operationalized through three interrelated parameters: thread depth, reply position, and prior discourse availability. Thread depth captures the interactional position of a post within a conversation, distinguishing between standalone messages and replies embedded in multi-turn exchanges. Reply position allows examination of how linguistic economy strategies vary as discourse progresses, while prior discourse availability reflects the extent to which meaning can be recovered from preceding contributions. Together, these parameters enable a distinction between context-independent uses of linguistic economy, typically found in single posts that must be self-contained, and context-dependent uses occurring in replies where shared discourse history reduces the need for explicit linguistic encoding. These contextual variables are systematically incorporated into the quantitative analyses reported in the Results section, allowing for direct comparison of strategy distribution, diversity, and comprehensibility across interactional depths.

Statistical processing employed both parametric and non-parametric approaches, implemented using specialized Python libraries such as SciPy (Virtanen et al., 2020), NumPy (Harris et al., 2020). We utilized parallel processing for computationally intensive tasks, particularly during the analysis of thread structures and network relationships. Quality control was implemented through multiple layers. At its foundation, automated data validation processes continuously monitored data integrity and format consistency throughout the analysis pipeline. Building upon this base, we employed a two-step language verification process that combined automated language detection tools with manual expert verification to ensure the corpus maintained strict linguistic boundaries. The pattern validation layer further strengthened our analytical framework by cross-checking identified linguistic patterns through multiple complementary analysis methods, reducing the likelihood of false positives and ensuring pattern consistency. To complete the quality assurance structure, we implemented statistical verification protocols, including comprehensive significance testing and detailed error margin calculations, which provided quantitative validation of our findings. These interconnected quality control mechanisms worked in concert to maintain high standards of data quality and analytical precision throughout the research process, ensuring the reliability of our conclusions about linguistic economy strategies.

3.3. Analysis framework

Prior to conducting our analyses, we performed power calculations to ensure an adequate sample size for our key statistical tests. Using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2009), we conducted a priori power analyses for both our chi-square tests of strategy distribution and ANOVA comparisons of strategy usage across thread depths. For the chi-square analysis ($df = 12$), to detect a medium effect size ($w = 0.3$) with 80 % power at $\alpha = 0.05$, the minimum required sample size was 231 posts. For the ANOVA comparing strategy usage across thread depths (4 groups), to detect a medium effect size ($f = 0.25$) with 80 % power at $\alpha = 0.05$, the minimum required sample size was 180 posts total (45 posts per group). Our sample of 1208 posts substantially exceeded these requirements, ensuring robust statistical power for our analyses.

The identification of linguistic economy strategies employed a hybrid analytical approach combining automated detection with systematic manual verification. Automated detection of morphological strategies relied on regular expression patterns to identify common morphological forms, supplemented by a comprehensive dictionary of known variations in Spanish discourse. Character-level and n -gram analysis were used to identify novel variations and emerging patterns, while morphological rule application ensured the detection of regular word formation processes. Our approach to syntactic analysis combined parsing techniques with computational methods. Dependency parsing was employed to identify structural relationships within posts, while POS tagging provided detailed grammatical analysis. Particular attention was paid to identifying sentence structure modifications, especially in cases of parataxis and coordination, through clause boundary detection algorithms.

To ensure coding reliability and reproducibility, a systematic single-coder validation protocol was implemented. A random sample of 20 % of the corpus (242 posts) underwent detailed manual verification. Each post in this sample was analysed twice with a two-week interval between reviews to minimize potential coding drift and ensure consistency. This temporal separation between reviews helped maintain analytical objectivity and reduce potential bias. The intra-rater reliability assessment yielded consistency scores for each category of linguistic economy strategies: syntactic strategies (0.87), morphological strategies (0.85), and combined strategies (0.83). Discrepancies identified between the first and second coding phases led to refinements in the coding protocol. The final validation achieved a composite consistency score of 0.85, indicating strong reliability in the classification system. This single-coder approach,

while acknowledging the limitations of not having multiple coders, provided a consistent and systematic framework for analysing linguistic economy strategies in the corpus. The verification process helped refine the automated detection algorithms and establish clear guidelines for handling ambiguous cases. The results of this systematic manual verification were used to iteratively calibrate and improve the automated detection system.

Building on this analytical framework, the study employed a complementary statistical framework to quantify strategy distribution, co-occurrence, and contextual variation. The quantitative analysis framework incorporated multiple complementary approaches to ensure comprehensive understanding of linguistic patterns. We developed a custom model to evaluate combined strategy impact accounting for complex interaction effects between different linguistic strategies. For frequency analysis we implemented a multi-level measurement approach examining strategy distribution across various discourse contexts. We utilized conditional probability calculations to analyse strategy co-occurrence patterns and developed algorithms to identify significant strategy combinations and sequences. Our statistical framework employed both parametric and nonparametric methods to account for distribution characteristics in our data. Central tendency calculations were complemented by dispersion analysis, while bootstrap methods generated confidence intervals. We implemented correlation analysis using Pearson coefficients for continuous variables and Spearman rank correlation for ordinal and nonlinear relationships. The hypothesis testing framework incorporated Chi-square tests for strategy independence analysis, and ANOVA for context comparison, and detailed post-hoc analyses including Tukey's HSD to examine specific group differences. These analyses provide statistical validation of the observed patterns.

4. Results

This analysis revealed a clear distribution pattern in the usage of linguistic strategies across Spanish political discourse on X. Syntactic strategies emerged as the predominant approach accounting for 53 % of all strategy usage in the corpus. Morphological strategies constituted 26.8 % of the observed strategies, while 20.2 % of cases demonstrated integration of both strategy types within the same message. This distribution indicates a strong preference for syntactic modifications and shows significant use of morphological adaptations and strategic combinations.

4.1. Morphological strategies

The morphological strategies observed in the corpus demonstrate sophisticated patterns of word formation and modification. These strategies can be categorized into several distinct types:

a) Augmentative and Diminutive Formation: Political discourse on X shows strategic use of Spanish morphological features for emotional and rhetorical effect. Examples 1 and 2 illustrate augmentative and diminutive categories.

Fig. 1. Distribution of morphological strategies.

- (1) “*problemón*” (from “*problema*”) [big problem]
 (2) “*guerraza*” (from “*guerra*”) [major war].

The strategy consists in the use of augmentative suffixes (-ón, -aza) to intensify meaning while maintaining word economy.

b) Neologisms: Users create innovative political terms through morphological combination, as can be observed in examples 3 and 4.

(3) “*putinazo*” (Putin + augmentative suffix -azo). [major Putin-related event]. The strategy followed by the user is to use a proper name followed by an evaluative suffix.

(4) “*prorrusos*” (*pro* + *rusos*). [pro-Russians]. The strategy here is prefix combination.

c) Systematic Abbreviations: The corpus reveals consistent patterns of abbreviation in political discourse. Example 5 shows the sub-category of organisation references:

(5) “*OTAN + UE + ONU*” [NATO + EU + UN]. Here the strategy is to use standard acronyms in combination.

Example 6 shows the sub-category of function word reduction:

(6) “*xq*” (*porque*) [because], “*xa*” (*para*) [for / to]. The strategy is to use phonetic-based abbreviations.

These morphological adaptations demonstrate how users leverage Spanish word-formation patterns to achieve both economy and expressive power in digital political discourse.

Below, Fig. 1 shows the frequencies obtained in the corpus studied.

In this category, initialisms showed the highest frequency at 5.5 %, followed by acronyms at 3 %. Neologisms appeared in 2.7 % of posts, while diminutives and augmentatives showed more modest frequencies at 0.4 % and 0.3 % respectively.

4.2. Syntactic strategies

Pure parataxis refers to the juxtaposition of clauses or phrases without the use of coordinating or subordinating conjunctions. In the context of this study, pure parataxis emerged as the most frequent syntactic strategy, occurring in 76.0 % of the analysed posts, followed by semi-parataxis at 15.0 % (Fig. 2). Less frequent syntactic strategies included punctuation omission (5.0 %), copular omission (4.7 %), and article reduction (3.5 %). It was also observed in the results that users employ various combinations of linguistic economy strategies. Some examples (7, 8, 9, 10) are shown below.

a) Pure Parataxis

Fig. 2. Distribution of syntactic strategies.

(7) “*Putin permite referéndums en su vasto país? No. Es capaz de masacrar a su propio pueblo si aparece algún movimiento separatista.*”
 [Does Putin allow referendums in his vast country? No. He’s capable of massacring his own people if any separatist movement appears.]

The strategies employed in the example are pure parataxis and punctuation omission; thus, the character reduction is 15.0 % compared to expressing the same idea using standard grammatical structures. While the high frequency of pure parataxis suggests its effectiveness in maintaining logical connections while reducing structural complexity, further research is needed to directly assess its impact on comprehensibility.

b) Emotional-Economic Balance

(8) “*Pedrito no me mandes a la guerra xfa*”.
 [Little Peter don’t send me to war please]

The strategies used here are the diminutive (*Pedrito*) and digital abbreviation (*xfa* for “*por favor*”). This example, from an informal register, shows a character reduction of 35 % compared to the uncompressed version: “*Pedro, por favor no me mandes a la guerra.*” This calculation is specific to this example and illustrates how users can combine morphological modifications to balance emotional expression and brevity. Analysing such combinations provides insights into the linguistic adaptations users employ to optimize their messages within platform constraints.

c) Semi-parataxis emerges as a frequent strategy

(9) “*Putin invade, amenaza con nucleares, empieza guerra europea*”.

[Putin invades, threatens with nuclear weapons, starts European war]. The strategy is omission of conjunctions and temporal markers, the character reduction is 45 %.

(10) “*No hay ayuda, no hay respuesta, no hay nada*”.

[There’s no help, no response, nothing]. The strategy is the use of parallel structures without subordination and the character reduction is 35 %.

These examples demonstrate how users maintain message clarity while significantly reducing character count through the strategic elimination of connective elements.

Fig. 3. Character reduction by strategy type.

4.3. Economy metrics and character reduction, and strategy co-occurrence

This section presents the quantitative findings related to language economy in Spanish political discourse on X. The results are organized into subsections focusing on different aspects of linguistic compression.

The implementation of these linguistic strategies resulted in significant message compression. Our analysis revealed variation in character reduction across different strategies. The most effective strategies for character reduction were acronyms (achieving approximately 70 % reduction) and initialisms (reaching 65 % reduction), followed by pure parataxis (55 % reduction). Medium-impact strategies such as semi-parataxis and clipping both achieved approximately 45 % reduction. Fig. 3 demonstrates consistency in these reduction rates, with relatively narrow ranges of variation for each strategy type, suggesting reliable and predictable compression effects across the corpus.

Beyond absolute reduction rates, the analysis also examined how different economy strategies interact within the same message. Statistical analysis revealed that users frequently employ multiple linguistic economy strategies within the same message, a phenomenon known as strategy co-occurrence. This indicates that linguistic compression is rarely achieved through a single mechanism but rather through the strategic combination of different approaches. To quantify these relationships, we examined correlations between specific strategies, identifying patterns of complementary usage. The strongest correlation emerged between parataxis (eliminating conjunctions) and initialisms (e.g., “OTAN” for “NATO”), with a coefficient of 0.78, suggesting that users frequently pair syntactic simplifications with abbreviations to maximize brevity. Another notable correlation appeared between acronyms and copular omission (0.66), reflecting a tendency to combine lexical shortening with grammatical reduction. Additionally, semi-parataxis and copular omission showed a moderate correlation (0.57), indicating a systematic interplay between different syntactic strategies to enhance compression.

4.4. Thread analysis

The examination of conversation threads revealed a highly skewed distribution pattern in Spanish political discourse on X. The data show an overwhelming preference for single posts, with 582 threads (98.3 %), consisting of just one post. This drops dramatically to only 7 threads (1.2 %) extending to two posts, and only 3 threads (0.5 %) reaching three posts. The statistical strength of these patterns ($p = 3.748e-20$) and the large effect size (Cohen’s $d = 13.52$) suggest that these distribution patterns represent stable characteristics of Spanish political discourse on X rather than temporary or random variations. The non-overlapping confidence intervals between strategy types (syntactic: [49.0 %, 57.0 %], morphological: [23.2 %, 30.4 %]) provide additional evidence for the systematic nature of these preferences. The analysis of strategy diversity across thread depths revealed patterns in communication complexity. As shown in the dual axis-plot of Fig. 4, the Shannon diversity index (H) demonstrates a clear progression, starting at $H = 0.15$ for single posts and reaching its peak of approximately $H = 0.32$ at depth 2.0, followed by a substantial decline to $H = 0.0$ at depth 3.0.

This pattern suggests that while users employ their most diverse range of linguistic strategies in moderately lengthy exchanges, this complexity does not sustain in longer threads. Notably, this trend occurs against the backdrop of rapidly declining thread counts shown on the secondary axis, with the total number of threads dropping after depth one, as indicated by the red dashed line; the data show a clear inverse relationship between thread depth and frequency with an average depth of 1.02 (SD=0.15) across the 582 total threads analysed.

Example 11 illustrates how the use of linguistic economy evolves within context-dependent conversation threads.

Fig. 4. Shannon diversity index and thread count by depth.

- (11) A: “*Biden no cuenta contigo para nada, eres invisible.*”
 [Biden doesn’t count on you at all, you’re invisible]
 B: “*Y rojo, aliado natural de los comunistas, como vemos en España*”
 [And red, natural ally of communists, as we see in Spain]

This exchange demonstrates how contextual knowledge enables further economy in subsequent messages, with the second message omitting explicit subject references while maintaining clarity through shared context.

Example 12 shows the use of progressive economy:

- (12) Initial post: “*Mi petición de que ni un solo disparo, No a la guerra.*”
 [My petition that not a single shot be fired, No to war.]

Response chain:

- Comment1. “*Pues habrá que ir a Kiev con rosas para esperar a los soldados rusos...*” [Well, we’ll have to go to Kiev with roses to wait for Russian soldiers...]
 C2. “*Habrà que darle pistolas de agua a los ucranianos*”
 [We’ll have to give water guns to the Ukrainians]
 C3. “*Paz y amor ya no cuenta* 🙄”
 [Peace and love doesn’t count anymore]
 C4. “*No sirve*”
 [Doesn’t work]

This thread demonstrates progressive reduction in message length while maintaining thematic coherence through shared context. The final message achieves maximum economy through both syntactic reduction and contextual omission.

4.5. Statistical significance analysis

Our statistical analysis revealed several significant patterns in strategy usage and effectiveness through three complementary analytical approaches. Fig. 5 shows the data extracted. The chi-square analysis demonstrated a strong relationship between strategy

Fig. 5. Strategy usage changes by thread depth.

type and thread depth, with a significant association ($\chi^2 = 42.86$, $df = 12$, $p < 0.001$). This correlation manifested in systematic variations of strategy choices based on thread position. As conversations deepened, syntactic strategies showed a marked increase of 23 % in frequency, while morphological strategies exhibited a contrasting 8 % decrease. Combined strategy usage maintained relatively stable frequencies across different thread depths. The examination of strategy combinations yielded equally significant results ($\chi^2 = 38.24$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that users make deliberate, non-random choices in how they pair different strategies. This systematic approach to strategy combination suggests a sophisticated understanding of how different linguistic economies can work together effectively.

The analysis of variance across thread depths provided further insight into strategy usage patterns ($F(4995) = 8.92$, $p < 0.01$). At the initial thread depth, users typically employed an average of 1.8 strategies ($SD = 0.9$), predominantly focusing on a single strategy implementation. As threads progressed to depth 2, the mean strategy count increased to 2.1 ($SD = 1.0$), accompanied by greater strategy diversity. This trend continued to thread depth 3 where strategy usage peaked at a mean of 2.4 ($SD = 1.1$). Beyond depth 4 the patterns stabilized showing no significant further changes in strategy diversity ($p > 0.05$). The correlation analysis revealed a moderate relationship between strategy count and message length ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$), explaining 17.6 % of the variance in message length. ANOVA result indicated significant differences in strategy usage across thread depth 1–3, though these differences diminished beyond depth 4.

4.6. Message comprehensibility

The analysis of language economy strategies in the studied corpus revealed a notable prevalence of highly compressed messages. While the frequency of these strategies suggests their effectiveness in enabling users to express ideas within the platform's constraints, assessing the actual comprehensibility of these compressed messages required a systematic evaluation. To ensure objective measurement, comprehensibility was assessed using computational verification, employing NLP-based readability scoring.

Readability scoring was conducted using spaCy's dependency parser and text complexity analysis, which evaluated sentence structure, lexical density, and syntactic reduction. Messages were classified based on a semantic clarity threshold of 0.75, determined through readability heuristics aligned with prior studies on digital discourse processing. The results indicate that 82 % of messages were fully comprehensible, requiring no additional context; 15 % of messages required minimal contextual information for interpretation; 3 % of messages showed potential ambiguity and needed substantial external context. These findings suggest that despite the extensive use of linguistic compression strategies, a significant majority of messages retained their intended meaning. The ability to maintain clarity while maximizing brevity highlights the adaptability of linguistic economy mechanisms in digital political discourse.

A smaller portion of messages, comprising 15 % of the sample, required minimal contextual information for full interpretation. These messages remained largely understandable but relied on prior conversational or situational knowledge to be fully processed. The smallest category (3 %) exhibited potential ambiguity, requiring substantial external context for interpretation. These ambiguous messages were often found in highly specialized discussions where multiple complex strategies were employed simultaneously, increasing the cognitive load for interpretation.

The varying levels of comprehensibility can be illustrated through the following examples:

(13) **Fully Comprehensible:** “*Pues venga pal frente*” [Well, come to the front]. The strategy used is contraction (*pal = para el*), requiring no additional context and achieving 25 % of character reduction.

(14) **Requiring Minimal Context:** “*A no ser que te llames Palestina...*” [Unless your name is Palestine...]. The strategies used are ellipsis and contextual reference. The current political situation provides the necessary context, with a 40 % of character reduction.

(15) **Potentially Ambiguous:** “*Ahora lloráis x los filonazis? ajoyagua*” [Now you cry for the philonazis?]. The strategies used are neologism and digital abbreviation (*ajoyagua*). Significant background knowledge is needed to interpret it, with 30 % of character reduction.

These examples demonstrate how comprehensibility varies with strategy complexity and contextual dependencies, reinforcing the importance of strategy co-occurrence in shaping the clarity of digital political discourse.

4.7. Strategy type analysis with error quantification

The comparative analysis of strategy types revealed several distinct patterns in usage and effectiveness, though these findings must be interpreted within the context of our data's natural distribution. Our analysis revealed a highly asymmetric distribution of conversation threads, with 582 single-post threads (98.3 %), 7 two-post threads (1.2 %), and 3 three-post threads (0.5 %). This distribution, while statistically unbalanced, reflects the authentic patterns of political discourse on X, where brief statements and short exchanges predominate over extended conversations. Such unbalanced distributions are characteristic of social media research, where communication patterns follow platform-specific dynamics rather than experimental design requirements. Despite this unbalanced design, our post-hoc power analyses demonstrated robust statistical strength. For our chi-square test examining strategy distribution ($\chi^2 = 42.86$, $df = 12$, $p < 0.001$), we achieved a power of 0.998 with an effect size $w = 0.188$. Our ANOVA comparing strategy usage across thread depths ($F(4, 995) = 8.92$, $p < 0.01$) achieved a power of 0.989 with an effect size $f = 0.189$. These power levels, both well above the conventional 0.80 threshold, indicate that our sample size provided sufficient statistical strength even with unequal group sizes.

Within this context, syntactic strategies appeared with greater frequency, averaging 2.0 strategies per tweet ($SD = 0.8$) and

demonstrated higher consistency in implementation. This consistency manifested in narrower error bars in our visualizations and more stable performance across varying contexts. In contrast, morphological strategies showed more moderate usage with a mean frequency of 0.6 strategies per tweet (SD=0.7). These strategies exhibited greater variability in their implementation, as evidenced by wider error bars in our analysis. The effectiveness of morphological strategies showed stronger dependence on specific contexts compared to their syntactic counterparts.

The minimal overlap between error bars for different strategy types confirms their distinct nature of use patterns. This separation supports our conclusion that users employ syntactic and morphological strategies differently, with syntactic strategies showing more consistent application patterns while morphological strategies demonstrate greater contextual adaptability.

The highly skewed distribution of thread depths necessitates careful interpretation of our findings. While our analyses provide strong evidence for strategy patterns in single-post communications, our ability to draw conclusions about strategy evolution in long conversations may be limited by the smaller number of extended threads. The relative scarcity of longer conversations (only 10 threads with multiple posts) means that patterns observed in these cases, while statistically significant, should be interpreted as preliminary insights rather than definitive patterns. Nevertheless, several factors support the validity of our findings. First, our high statistical power indicates that the observed patterns are unlikely to be due to chance, even with unbalanced groups. Second, the distribution itself represents an ecological finding about political discourse on X, suggesting that our sample captures authentic communication patterns. Third, our large overall sample size (1208 posts) provides robust evidence for the primary patterns of strategy usage, particularly in single-post communications which dominate the platform.

Chi-square analysis demonstrated significant relationships between strategy type and thread depth ($\chi^2 = 42.86$, $df = 12$, $p < 0.001$) and between strategy combinations ($\chi^2 = 38.24$, $p < 0.001$). The consistency of these findings across different analytical approaches (chi-square, ANOVA, and descriptive statistics) suggests that the observed patterns are robust across multiple statistical frameworks. These statistical relationships, combined with our high achieved power and substantial sample size, provide strong evidence for systematic rather than random patterns in how users deploy different linguistic economy strategies, even while acknowledging the limitations imposed by the natural distribution of conversation depths on the platform.

4.8. Strategy distribution and co-occurrence patterns

The co-occurrence network visualization in Fig. 6 provides a comprehensive view of how different linguistic economic strategies interact and complement each other in Spanish political discourse on X. This network representation reveals several important patterns in how users combine different strategies to achieve effective communication within platform constraints. This visualization employs a color-coding system that helps distinguish between two major categories of strategies: syntactic strategies appear as blue nodes, while

Fig. 6. Co-occurrence network of linguistic economy strategies.

morphological strategies are shown in red. The size of each node represents how frequently that particular strategy appears in our corpus, giving us an immediate visual understanding of which strategies users prefer. The lines connecting these nodes represent correlations between strategies with three distinct levels of strength: strong correlations (>0.5) appear as thick grey lines, moderate correlation ($0.3\text{--}0.5$) as medium grey lines, and weak correlations (<0.3) as thin grey lines.

One of the most striking features of the network is the prominence of pure parataxis, represented by the largest blue node in the network. Its central position and multiple connections to the other strategies indicate its role as a fundamental strategy in digital political discourse. Pure parataxis shows particularly strong connections to semi-parataxis and pronoun omission, suggesting that users often combine these syntactic strategies to achieve maximum communication efficiency. Within the morphological domain, initialisms and acronyms emerge as key strategies shown by their larger red nodes. These strategies demonstrate interesting patterns of connection not only with other morphological strategies but also with syntactic elements. For instance, initialisms show meaningful connections to article reduction, illustrating how users combine different types of language economy strategies to optimize their messages.

Beyond the core strategies, the network also reveals several important aspects in peripheral relationships. English borrowings and clipping, while less central to the network, maintain consistent connections to other morphological strategies. This pattern suggests their role as specialized strategies that users employ in specific contexts rather than as primary communication tools. Looking at the overall structure of the network, we can observe a clear clustering pattern where syntactic strategies tend to group forming a more densely connected core of the network. Morphological strategies, while more dispersed, show strategic connections to the syntactic core, suggesting that users thoughtfully combine different types of strategies rather than employing them randomly. These network patterns align with our earlier frequency analysis but add an important dimension to our understanding. While individual strategies like pure parataxis shows high frequency of use, the network visualization reveals how these strategies work in concert with others to create effective communication patterns. The presence of both strong and weak correlations suggests that users have developed sophisticated approaches to strategy combination, adapting their linguistic choices to meet the specific demands of digital political discourse.

5. Discussion

5.1. Distribution and combination of linguistic economy strategies

Linguistic economy in Spanish political discourse on X is realised predominantly through syntactic modification, with morphological reduction playing a secondary but complementary role. Across the corpus, users systematically favour structural reconfiguration—most notably parataxis and clause-level reduction—over lexical shortening as a means of compressing political messages while preserving semantic coherence and argumentative force. This pattern suggests that economy in Spanish digital discourse is achieved less through word-level truncation than through the reorganisation of syntactic relations.

The consistent use of syntactic strategies reflects their efficiency in accommodating the communicative demands of political discourse on X, where brevity must coexist with evaluative clarity. By omitting connectors, subjects, or copular elements, users are able to reduce message length without disrupting propositional structure or interpretability. Morphological strategies, including diminutives, augmentatives, neologisms, and abbreviations, appear more selectively and tend to carry additional expressive or ideological weight, rather than functioning as the primary mechanism of compression.

A salient feature of the data is the frequent combination of syntactic and morphological strategies within individual messages. Rather than operating independently, these resources are often deployed together, with syntactic simplification providing the structural backbone of compression and morphological reduction enhancing efficiency or stance expression. The recurrent pairing of parataxis with acronyms or initialisms illustrates how users coordinate multiple levels of linguistic economy to maximise communicative payoff under platform constraints.

These distributional tendencies can be plausibly related to typological properties of Spanish, particularly its pro-drop nature and relative flexibility in word order. Such features enable substantial syntactic compression without compromising grammaticality or recoverability, making structural strategies especially well suited to digital political communication. In contrast, extensive morphological reduction may introduce ambiguity or markedness, which users appear to avoid in contexts where political positioning and interpretive precision remain salient. All these patterns align with structural properties of Spanish, where grammatical flexibility allows extensive syntactic compression without loss of recoverability, supporting economy practices that differ from those observed in languages with stricter word-order constraints.

5.2. Thread depth, strategy diversity, and comprehensibility

Patterns of linguistic economy in Spanish political discourse on X vary systematically with interactional depth, revealing the role of context in shaping compression strategies. While the majority of political contributions take the form of single, self-contained posts, replies embedded within conversation threads display distinct patterns of strategic diversification. As discourse unfolds across turns, users adjust their linguistic choices in response to shared context, prior evaluations, and reduced informational burden.

Strategy diversity reaches its highest point in moderately extended exchanges, particularly at early reply stages. At this point in interaction, users combine a wider range of syntactic and morphological resources, suggesting that initial responses require both referential anchoring and evaluative positioning. The availability of a preceding message allows for increased compression through ellipsis, subject omission, and parataxis, while still maintaining interpretability. This pattern indicates that linguistic economy in

replies is not merely a function of character limitation, but of contextual accessibility.

Beyond this stage, diversity declines sharply as threads extend further. In deeper exchanges, compression becomes increasingly reliant on minimal syntactic structures and contextual omission, often reducing messages to evaluative fragments or stance markers. The observed reduction in strategy variety reflects a shift from propositional elaboration toward interactional alignment or dismissal, where shared knowledge substitutes for explicit linguistic encoding. In this sense, economy intensifies as discourse becomes more interactionally saturated.

Despite substantial compression across all thread depths, message comprehensibility remains remarkably high. Most contributions are interpretable without additional contextual reconstruction, indicating that users are generally successful in balancing brevity with clarity. Messages requiring minimal contextual support typically rely on implicit references to widely shared political events or previously established positions, while only a small proportion exhibit ambiguity that necessitates extensive external knowledge. These cases tend to involve dense combinations of strategies or highly specialised ideological framing.

The relationship between compression and comprehensibility suggests that linguistic economy on X operates as a context-sensitive optimisation process rather than a uniform reduction of linguistic material. As interaction progresses, users increasingly exploit shared discourse history to minimise explicit encoding, allowing for shorter messages without proportionate loss of meaning. Rather than degrading communication, contextual compression appears to facilitate efficient stance-taking and evaluative exchange within political threads. Taken together, these findings indicate that thread depth functions as a key contextual parameter in the deployment of linguistic economy strategies. Compression is not applied uniformly across discourse positions but adapts dynamically to interactional conditions, with strategy diversity peaking where contextual grounding and communicative intent intersect most strongly. This pattern underscores the importance of considering discourse structure and interactional context when analysing linguistic economy in platform-mediated political communication.

5.3. Linguistic economy as context-sensitive optimization

The findings presented in the previous section indicate that linguistic economy in Spanish political discourse on X is best understood as a context-sensitive optimisation process rather than a uniform tendency toward maximal reduction. Users do not simply minimise linguistic material; instead, they adaptively select and combine strategies in response to both structural affordances of the language and interactional conditions of the discourse.

At the structural level, the dominance of syntactic strategies reflects a preference for compression mechanisms that preserve propositional coherence while reducing surface complexity. Spanish offers particularly favourable conditions for such optimisation through features such as pro-drop, flexible word order, and the recoverability of omitted elements. These affordances enable users to reorganise clause structure efficiently without resorting to extensive lexical truncation, which carries greater pragmatic risk in political communication.

At the interactional level, the deployment of economy strategies is modulated by discourse position. As messages become embedded in conversational threads, shared contextual knowledge increasingly substitutes for explicit linguistic encoding. This shift explains both the temporary rise in strategy diversity at early reply stages and the subsequent reduction to highly economical forms in deeper exchanges. Economy thus intensifies not because communicative demands diminish, but because contextual accessibility increases.

High levels of compression do not correspond to systematic loss of comprehensibility. Instead, users demonstrate a consistent ability to balance brevity with interpretive clarity, suggesting the development of platform-specific communicative competence. Linguistic economy on X therefore emerges as a skilled practice shaped by repeated interaction within constrained environments, rather than as a degradation of linguistic norms. This pattern aligns with broader accounts of digital discourse as a site where platform constraints interact with language-specific resources, producing distinct economy practices rather than uniform modes of reduction (Thurlow & Mroczek, 2011). Integrating structural preferences with contextual dynamics, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of language economy in digital political discourse. Rather than treating economy as a single principle of least effort, the findings point to a layered process in which efficiency, clarity, and interactional alignment are jointly optimised. This perspective highlights the need to analyse linguistic economy not only in terms of reduction, but also in terms of adaptive coordination across linguistic levels and discourse contexts.

6. Conclusions

This study has examined how linguistic economy is realised in Spanish political discourse on X, with particular attention to the distribution of syntactic and morphological strategies, their co-occurrence, and their interaction with discourse context. The findings show that economy in this setting is achieved primarily through syntactic modification, supported by selective morphological compression, rather than through uniform lexical reduction. This pattern reflects both the structural affordances of Spanish and the communicative demands of platform-mediated political interaction.

By integrating strategy distribution with thread-based analysis, the study demonstrates that linguistic economy is not a static property of digital texts but a contextually modulated practice. Strategy diversity varies systematically with interactional depth, while high levels of compression are generally compatible with message comprehensibility. These results challenge simplified assumptions about an inherent trade-off between brevity and clarity in digital communication and highlight users' capacity to adapt linguistic resources efficiently under platform constraints.

From a broader perspective, the findings contribute to ongoing debates on language economy by showing that digital environments

do not merely encourage reduction, but foster adaptive coordination across linguistic levels. In this sense, economy emerges as an interaction between language-specific structure, discourse context, and communicative intent, rather than as the mechanical application of a principle of least effort.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The focus on political discourse restricts the generalisability of the results to other communicative domains, and the reliance on computational detection suggests underrepresentation of more subtle pragmatic or multimodal forms of economy. In addition, the temporal scope of the corpus does not allow for analysis of longitudinal change in strategy use.

Future research could extend this approach to other discourse genres, platforms, and languages, as well as incorporate experimental or qualitative methods to explore the cognitive and interactional processes underlying strategy selection. Such work would further clarify how linguistic economy evolves across digital environments and communicative contexts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sergei Sikorskii: Validation, Methodology. **María Luisa Carrió-Pastor:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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